

Education Quarterly Reviews

Salee, A., & Sanitlou, N. (2024). The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 7(4), 96-106.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.07.04.527

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools

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Abstract

The objectives of this research were 1) To study the use of Information technology for school administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools. 2) To compare the use of Information technology for school administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, classified by educational qualifications, tenure status, school size, and varying work experiences; and 3) To examine approaches to the use of Information technology for school administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools. The research method is divided into two steps Step 1 Study and compare the use of Information technology for school administration. The sample group includes 251 administrators and teachers from within Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, selected through stratified random sampling based on the proportion of teachers in each school. The research instrument is a questionnaire on the use of Information technology for school administration, created by the researcher, and designed using a 5-level rating scale. Data are analyzed using the mean and standard deviation. Step 2 Study the approach to the use of Information technology for school administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools. The informants include three experts selected by purposive sampling. The tools used for data collection include an interview form on the use of Information technology for school administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools. Data were analyzed using content analysis. The research results found that: 1) the use of Information technology for school administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools was at a high level overall. When considering each aspect, the area with the highest average score was general administration, also at a high level. 2) Administrators and teachers with different educational qualifications used information technology in administration differently, as classified by the educational qualification variable. 3) The results also suggest that in terms of academic administration, ICT and Hybrid Learning should be utilized to develop mobile classrooms, digital media, assessment methods, and to enhance parental participation. In budget administration, funds should be allocated for learning equipment, disease prevention, software and internet investment, and using Big Data to improve learning. For personnel administration, online work systems should be adopted, teachers' digital skills should be developed, Hybrid Learning should be promoted, and leadership should follow the Super Coach model. In general administration, online systems should be used to track students, develop websites, and create digital media archives. Additionally, equipment for online teaching should be allocated.

Keywords: The Use of Information Technology, School Administration, Sarasas Affiliated Area 3 Schools

1. Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving world of technology and communication, human behavior has shifted from an analog to a digital era. Information exchange occurs swiftly, making the 21st century an age of global society and economy that demands adaptation. Individuals must continuously develop and engage in lifelong learning to be prepared for changes and challenges brought by innovations and digital technologies (Office of the Education Council, 2017). Thailand has prioritized the use of technology in education, incorporating it into the core curriculum and promoting STEM education. Additionally, the country has implemented school-based management to enhance educational quality, aligning with global changes (Office of the Education Council, 2021).

Innovation in school management is essential for educational development, and successful strategies from countries like Singapore, Japan, and South Korea should be applied. These strategies include increasing autonomy in school management and integrating technology into teaching and administration. Educational laws and policies regarding the use of information technology (IT) in school management aim to enhance learning and administrative efficiency, reduce teachers' paperwork, and streamline complex processes (Ministry of Education, 2011). Effective implementation of these innovations depends on the collaboration between administrators, teachers, and educational personnel, leading to optimal outcomes (Usman Leesannmahmad, 2017). Research on the use of IT in school management is crucial. Sarasas schools have adapted by utilizing technology to respond to the digital world's changes, improving efficiency and flexibility in school operations (Sarasas School Journal, 2017). Therefore, this research focuses on studying the use of IT in school management within Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, aiming to assess the level of IT usage and develop guidelines for future improvements. Effective use of IT by school administrators leads to the progress of educational institutions, aligning them with the learning society of the modern age, benefitting both policy and practice in the administration of schools.

1.1. Research Objectives

1. To study The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools.
2. To compare The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, differences in educational qualifications, job positions, school sizes, and work experience.
3. To explore guidelines for The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools

1.2. Research Hypotheses

In this study, the researcher formulated the following research hypotheses

1. The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools., is at a moderate level.
2. The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, varies significantly based on differences in educational qualifications, job positions, school sizes, and work experience.

Literature Review

The research on The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, includes an examination of relevant documents, theories, and studies as follows:

Sitthichai Seemi (2023) defines school management as a collaborative process among key individuals involved in education management, aimed at enhancing the quality of schools. This is achieved through the efficient and optimal use of available resources to foster the development of students in knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, ethics, and morality. This is facilitated through organizational structure, management practices, support for operations, and ongoing process improvement to meet established educational goals.

Busara Bunta-la (2020) asserts that information technology is a crucial tool for organizational operations and educational management today. The benefits of information technology allow for the rapid and high-quality

processing of daily data into accurate and relevant information for educational administrators. Additionally, it provides organizations with a competitive advantage in both education and business sectors. The utilization of information technology should be complemented by other resources to achieve maximum efficiency. Furthermore, information technology plays a significant role in national development across various sectors, including politics, governance, society, public health, transportation, and security, particularly in education, where it enhances knowledge development and educational management.

Jitjaroon Songwiya (2018) states that school management encompasses all operations within a school to align with educational objectives or curriculum goals. This includes ensuring that students maintain good health, possess moral integrity, become responsible citizens, and apply their acquired knowledge for participation in the economy and social development. According to the National Education Act of 1999 and its amendment (No. 2) of 2002, the act emphasizes decentralizing management and decision-making to operational units, namely schools and educational service areas. Central management is tasked with setting policies, planning, budgeting, and assessing educational quality and standards, covering four key areas: 1) Academic Management, 2) Budget and Financial Management, 3) Personnel Management, and 4) General Administration.

In summary, the application of information technology in school management refers to the integration of information and communication technology, which encompasses computer technology and interconnected telecommunication networks, aimed at enhancing efficiency and speed in analyzing, processing, and storing data. This facilitates timely utilization for effective school management, categorized into four areas: 1) Academic Management, 2) Budget Management, 3) Personnel Management, and 4) General Administration.

2. Research Methodology

Step 1: Study and Compare The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, Categorized by Educational Qualification, Position Status, School Size, and Varying Work Experience

Population and Sample Used in the Research

1. Population
 - The population for this research includes administrators and teachers from Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, totaling 721 individuals.
2. Sample
 - The sample size was determined using G*Power version 3.1.9.2. The statistical test was set to Correlation Bivariate Normal Model, with a power analysis of 0.99 and a significance level of 0.01. The effect size was set to medium (0.3) based on Cohen (1977) as cited in Niphathorn Sanitlue, Watcharaporn Satrphet, and Yada Napaarak (2018), resulting in a sample size of 251 individuals.

2.1. Research Instruments

The data collection tool used in this research was a questionnaire developed by the researcher, based on a review of academic documents and related research. The questionnaire consists of two parts:

1. Part 1: Respondent Demographics
 - This part includes questions in a checklist format regarding the respondent's status.
2. Part 2: Use of Information Technology in Educational Administration
 - This section contains 22 questions regarding The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, using a 5-point Likert scale:
 - 5: Very High Usage
 - 4: High Usage
 - 3: Moderate Usage
 - 2: Low Usage
 - 1: Very Low Usage

2.2. Development of Research Instruments

The development process of the data collection instrument was as follows:

1. A review of theoretical concepts and frameworks relevant to The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools
2. Creation of the questionnaire addressing The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, divided into two sections:
 - Section 1: Demographics of respondents, including position status, school size, and work experience in a checklist format.
 - Section 2: Aspects of using information technology in educational administration across four areas:
 1. Academic Management
 2. Budget Management
 3. Personnel Management
 4. General Administration
 5. This section utilizes a 5-point Likert scale (Very High, High, Moderate, Low, Very Low).
3. The completed questionnaire was presented to the advisor for review and feedback for improvements.
4. The revised questionnaire was then presented to three experts selected based on their knowledge, experience, and expertise in educational administration and technology. The experts assessed content validity and the appropriateness of the language used by calculating the Index of Item Objective Congruency (IOC).
5. The finalized questionnaire underwent a trial run (Try-Out) with teachers outside the sample group.
6. Reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach's alpha coefficient method (Cronbach, 1990:202-204), yielding an IOC value of 0.97.
7. The finalized questionnaire was used to collect data from the sample group.

2.3. Data Collection

The data collection for this research was conducted as follows:

1. The researcher coordinated with the Graduate School, Faculty of Education and Liberal Arts, Suvarnabhumi Institute of Technology, to obtain permission to collect data for the research.
2. The researcher distributed the questionnaire along with a letter requesting cooperation in the research to administrators and teachers in Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools Follow-up was conducted for any outstanding questionnaires.
3. The researcher reviewed the returned questionnaires for data verification.
4. The collected questionnaires were analyzed for data.

2.4. Data Analysis

The researcher analyzed the data in the following manner:

1. All returned questionnaires were checked for accuracy and completeness, and those deemed complete were further analyzed.
2. Selected questionnaires were scored according to predetermined criteria.
3. Data analysis was performed using software, covering:
 - 3.1 General information about respondents, including position status, school size, and work experience, analyzed through frequency distribution and percentage calculation.
 - 3.2 The level of use of information technology in educational administration was analyzed using mean ($\bar{X}$) and standard deviation (S.D.).
 - 3.3 Comparison of information technology usage in educational administration categorized by position status, school size, and work experience. If differences were detected, pairwise comparisons were conducted using Scheffé's method.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

The statistics used for data analysis included:

1. Quality Assessment of the Instrument: 1.1 Calculation of the Index of Item - Objective Congruence (IOC). 1.2 Reliability assessment of the questionnaire using Cronbach's alpha coefficient (Cronbach, 1990:202-204).
2. Data Analysis Statistics: 2.1 Percentage calculations. 2.2 Mean calculations. 2.3 Standard deviation calculations.
3. Hypothesis Testing Statistics: 3.1 Analysis of the level of information technology usage in educational administration, using mean ($\bar{X}$) and standard deviation (S.D.). 3.2 Comparison of information technology usage in educational administration categorized by position status, school size, and work experience, using t-tests and one-way ANOVA. In cases of differences, Scheffé's method was used for pairwise comparison.

Step 2: Study Guidelines for The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools

2.6. Informants

The informants included three experts selected purposefully (Purposive Sampling) based on the following criteria:

1. Expert in Educational Administration:
 - One senior executive responsible for policy-making in educational administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, holding a doctoral degree.
2. Educational Administrators:
 - Two educational administrators with at least a master's degree or equivalent, having the position of at least Senior Director or Senior Deputy Director, with a minimum of 5 years of management experience, and expertise in information technology or educational technology.

2.7. Data Collection Instruments

For the study of guidelines for The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools, the researcher employed a structured interview format divided into two parts:

1. Part 1: General Information of Interviewees:
 - This part included open-ended questions.
2. Part 2: Guidelines for Using Information Technology:
 - This section addressed four areas:
 1. Academic Management
 2. Budget Management
 3. Personnel Management
 4. General Administration

2.8. Development and Quality Assessment of Data Collection Instruments

1. Review of literature on interview principles and question formulation to ensure comprehensive coverage of the content area.
2. Study of relevant documents and research on the use of information technology in educational administration.
3. Establishment of a research framework categorized into four areas for the development of interview questions.
4. Formulation of interview questions based on data obtained from the study of information technology usage in educational administration.
5. The interview questions were refined according to suggestions from the advisor.
6. Finalized interview questions were printed and prepared for data collection.

2.9. Data Collection

The researcher conducted data collection as follows:

1. Coordination with the Graduate School, Faculty of Education and Liberal Arts, Suvarnabhumi Institute of Technology, to obtain permission for interviews.
2. Submission of a request letter for cooperation to administrators of schools within Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools
3. The researcher scheduled interviews with selected experts, arranging dates, times, and locations.
4. Conducted interviews based on the predetermined guidelines in the interview format.

2.10. Data Analysis

The data obtained from the interviews were organized and summarized through content analysis.

3. Research Results

Table 1: The mean and standard deviation of the interpretation and The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools.

		Level of Implementation		Interpretation	Rank
Use of Information Technology		$\bar{x}$	S.D.		
1	Academic Administration	4.42	0.18	High	2
2	Budget Administration	4.25	0.17	High	3
3	Human Resource Administration	4.13	0.13	High	4
4	General Administration	4.61	0.13	High	1
Overall (X_{tot})		4.35	0.05	สูง	

From Table 1, it is evident that the overall The Use of Information Technology for School Administration under Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.35$, S.D. = 0.05). The rankings of the mean values from highest to lowest are as follows: General Administration is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.61$, S.D. = 0.15), Academic Administration is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.42$, S.D. = 0.18), Budget Administration is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.25$, S.D. = 0.17), and Human Resource Administration is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.13$, S.D. = 0.13).

Table 2: The use of information technology in school administration based on educational qualifications among schools in the Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools

		Bachelor's Degree (n=224)		Postgraduate Degree (n=27)		t	p
Use of Information Technology		$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.		
1	Academic Administration	4.40	0.17	4.64	0.06	-14.60	0.00
2	Budget Administration	4.27	0.17	4.09	0.10	7.74	0.00
3	Human Resource Administration	4.13	0.13	4.08	0.10	1.99	0.01
4	General Administration	4.58	0.14	4.83	0.00	-25.33	0.00

Overall (X_{tot})	4.34	0.05	4.41	0.04	-5.85	0.00
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*p < .05

From Table 2, it is found that the use of information technology in school administration among schools in the Sarasas affiliated area 3 schools differs significantly based on educational qualifications at the .05 level. Teachers with postgraduate degrees and those with bachelor's degrees showed differences in the use of information technology across all four areas.

Table 3: The use of information technology in school administration based on the position held.

Use of Information Technology	School Administrators (n=50)		Teacher (n=201)		t	p
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.		
1 Academic Administration	4.41	0.30	4.43	0.14	-0.46	0.64
2 Budget Administration	4.22	0.20	4.26	0.16	-1.15	0.24
3 Human Resource Administration	4.13	0.19	4.12	0.11	0.23	0.81
4 General Administration	4.69	0.16	4.59	0.14	3.72	0.00
Overall (X_{tot})	4.36	0.07	4.35	0.05	1.02	0.30

*p < .05

From Table 3, it is found that the overall use of information technology in school administration does not significantly differ based on the position held. However, when considering specific areas, school administrators and teachers showed a significant difference in the use of information technology in General Administration.

Table 4: The use of information technology in school administration based on school size.

Use of Information Technology	Source of Variation	df	ss	ms	f	p
1 Academic Administration	Between Groups	2	2.46	1.23	51.22	0.00
	Within Groups	248	5.97	0.02		
	Total	250	8.44			
2 Budget Administration	Between Groups	2	1.30	0.65	25.47	0.00
	Within Groups	248	6.34	0.02		
	Total	250	7.64			
3 Human Resource Administration	Between Groups	2	0.49	0.24	14.61	0.00
	Within Groups	248	4.18	0.01		
	Total	250	4.67			
4 General Administration	Between Groups	2	1.77	0.88	49.20	0.00
	Within Groups	248	4.47	0.01		
	Total	250	6.25			
Overall	Between Groups	2	0.09	0.04	16.05	0.00
	Within Groups	248	0.73	0.00		
	Total	250	0.83			

*p < .05

From Table 4, it is found that the use of information technology in school administration varies significantly based on school size at the .05 level.

Table 5: The use of information technology in school administration based on work experience.

Use of Information Technology	Source of Variation	df	ss	ms	f	p
1 Academic Administration	Between Groups	2	0.65	0.32	10.36	0.00
	Within Groups	248	7.79	0.03		
	Total	250	8.44			
2 Budget Administration	Between Groups	2	0.65	0.32	11.59	0.00
	Within Groups	248	6.99	0.02		
	Total	250	7.64			
3 Human Resource Administration	Between Groups	2	0.16	0.08	4.59	0.01
	Within Groups	248	4.50	0.01		
	Total	250	4.67			
4 General Administration	Between Groups	2	0.80	0.40	18.27	0.00
	Within Groups	248	5.45	0.02		
	Total	250	6.25			
Overall	Between Groups	2	0.22	0.11	3.32	0.03
	Within Groups	248	0.80	0.03		
	Total	250	0.83			

*p < .05

From Table 5, it was found that the use of information technology in the administration of educational institutions within Sarasas affiliated area 3, categorized by work experience, shows statistically significant differences overall and in each dimension at the .05 level.

4. Data Analysis Results

The analysis of data on the use of information technology in the administration of educational institutions within the Sarasas network in Education Zone 3 was synthesized from in-depth interviews with three experts. The researcher employed content analysis techniques, which yielded the following conclusions:

1. **Academic Administration:** It is recommended to utilize ICT and Hybrid Learning, develop mobile classrooms, digital media, assessment tools, and enhance parental involvement.
2. **Budget Administration:** Allocate budgets for educational equipment, disease prevention measures, invest in software and internet access, and leverage Big Data to improve learning outcomes.
3. **Human Resource Administration:** It is necessary to adjust online systems, develop teachers' digital skills, promote Hybrid Learning, and adopt the role of a Super Coach.
4. **General Administration:** Implement online systems to monitor students, develop websites and digital resource repositories, and allocate equipment for online teaching.

5. Discussion of Research Findings

The research findings on the opinions of administrators and teachers from the Sarasas network in Education Zone 3 highlight several key points for discussion:

The use of information technology in the administration of educational institutions within the Sarasas network in Education Zone 3 was found to be at a high level, both overall and in each area, particularly in four main aspects: academic administration, budget administration, human resource administration, and general administration. A significant factor contributing to the widespread use of technology is the COVID-19 pandemic, which prompted all organizations to adapt and effectively implement technology in their operations. These findings align with the research conducted by Kritiphatkorn Siripathnitphokin (2021), which indicated a high level of technology use in educational administration across all four areas during the new normal era.

5.1. Academic Administration

In the Sarasas network within Education Zone 3, the use of information technology in academic administration was reported at a high level. The top three applications are as follows:

1. Utilization of technology and capable programs for the development of school curricula.
2. Use of technology for the development of media, innovations, and learning resources.
3. Leveraging technology to foster collaboration in academic development with other educational institutions.

Conversely, the least applied area was the use of technology for research aimed at improving educational quality and the development of internal quality assurance systems within educational institutions. This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Phichayanee Kahlong (2017), which found that the use of information technology for academic administration in basic education institutions under the Chaiyaphum Primary Educational Service Area Office was also high.

5.2. Budget Administration

The use of information technology for budget administration in the Sarasas network within Education Zone 3 was reported at a high level, with the top three applications being:

1. Employing technology or ready-made programs for budget allocation.
2. Monitoring, evaluating, and reporting on the use of funds and the performance of financial management through technology or ready-made programs.
3. Utilizing technology or ready-made programs for accounting and management of materials and assets.

The least applied area was the use of technology or ready-made programs for managing accounts, materials, and assets. This information corresponds with the research of Worawut Lamjan (2020), which found that administrators of private schools in the Phatthalung Primary Educational Service Area also utilized information technology for budget administration at a high level, highlighting the significant role of technology in enhancing efficiency and transparency in budget management.

5.3. Human Resource Administration

In the Sarasas network within Education Zone 3, the use of information technology for human resource administration was also reported at a high level, with the top three applications being:

1. Use of technology for defining positions, recruitment, and appointments.
2. Implementation of technology to enhance the efficiency of administrative operations.
3. Utilizing technology for workforce planning.

The least applied area was the use of technology for storing and maintaining personnel discipline data. This information aligns with the study conducted by Phakkorn Boonpan (2020), which found that the use of information technology for administrative functions in educational institutions under the Bueng Kan Primary Educational Service Area Office was similarly high, indicating the effectiveness of technology in supporting human resource management in educational settings.

5.4. General Administration

In the Sarasas network within Education Zone 3, the use of information technology for general administration was reported at a high level, with the top three applications being:

1. Use of technology or programs for administrative operations.
2. Development of information network systems through technology or programs.
3. Coordination and development of educational networks through technology to promote student affairs, educational publicity, and resource mobilization for education.

The least applied area was the use of technology for organizational development management, site organization, and environmental conditions. This information corresponds with the research of Usman Leesamhamat (2017), which found that the use of technology in general administration within secondary schools in the Secondary Educational Service Area 16 was also high.

5.5. Comparison of Information Technology Use in Educational Administration

The study found significant statistical differences at the .05 level in the use of information technology in educational administration among administrators and teachers in the Sarasas network within Education Zone 3, categorized by educational qualifications, position status, school size, and work experience.

1. **Educational Qualifications:** Administrators and teachers with varying educational qualifications showed significant differences in the use of information technology at the .05 level. Higher educational qualifications likely enhance the ability to utilize technology more effectively in administration, aligning with the research of Usman Leesamhamat (2017), which found clear differences in technology use in administration among secondary schools based on educational qualifications.
2. **Position Status:** Administrators and teachers with different position statuses exhibited no significant differences in the overall use of information technology for educational administration. However, when considering individual aspects, significant differences were observed in general administration at the .05 level. This finding corresponds with the study by Kanokwan Changlom (2016), which identified significant differences in technology use in general administration among various position holders in local administrative organizations in Pathum Thani province.
3. **School Size:** Administrators and teachers in schools of different sizes demonstrated significant differences in the use of information technology at the .05 level, with larger schools being better equipped with technology compared to medium-sized schools. This finding is consistent with the research of Jarunan Phiewphang (2021), which found variations in technology use according to school size in the Nakhon Phanom educational service area.
4. **Work Experience:** Additionally, administrators and teachers with differing levels of experience displayed significant differences in their use of technology for administration, with more experienced individuals demonstrating better effectiveness in utilizing technology.

5.6. Interviews on the Use of Information Technology in Educational Administration

The results from in-depth interviews with three administrators from the Sarasas network in Education Zone 3 revealed the following conclusions based on the interview questions:

1. **Recommendations for Academic Administration:** It is suggested to use ICT and Hybrid Learning, develop mobile classrooms, digital media, assessment tools, and enhance parental involvement.
2. **Recommendations for Budget Administration:** Allocate budgets for educational equipment, disease prevention measures, invest in software and internet access, and leverage Big Data for improved learning outcomes.
3. **Recommendations for Human Resource Administration:** Adjust online systems, develop teachers' digital skills, promote Hybrid Learning, and adopt the role of a Super Coach.
4. **Recommendations for General Administration:** Implement online systems for student monitoring, develop websites and digital resource repositories, and allocate equipment for online teaching.

6. Recommendations from the Research

1. Educational institutions within the Sarasas network in Education Zone 3 should utilize technology or capable programs for research aimed at improving educational quality and internal quality assurance systems.
2. Educational administrators should adopt technology or ready-made programs for accounting, material management, and asset administration.
3. Schools should implement technology or tools for storing disciplinary records and maintaining discipline.
4. Medium-sized schools within the Sarasas network in Education Zone 3, which exhibit lower usage of information technology, should increase their adoption of technology.

7. Suggestions for Future Research

1. Future studies should evaluate the effectiveness of information technology usage in educational administration.

2. It is recommended to investigate factors influencing the utilization of information technology in educational administration.

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to this research.

Funding: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

References

- Kritiphatakorn Siripattanithiphokin. (2021). The use of technology in the management of educational administrators in the new normal era under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Krabi. *Proceedings of the 12th Hat Yai National and International Academic Conference*, Hatyai University, 1344-1361.
- Kanokwan Changlom. (2016). Issues and needs for the use of information technology in the management of academic affairs according to the opinions of educational administrators and teachers under the local government organization in Pathum Thani Province. *Eastern Asia University Academic Journal*, 6(2), 66-78.
- Jarunun Phiwphang. (2021). Digital leadership affecting the use of information technology and communication in the management of educational administrators under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Nakhon Phanom, Zone 2. *Rajapark Journal*, 15(39), 96-108.
- Jitjaroon Songwittaya. (January - June 2018). Management skills of educational administrators. *Journal of Roikaensarn Academy*, 3(1), 41-57.
- Chaiya Buahom. (2020). The use of information technology in the management of personnel at Nam Kliang Wittaya School. Sisaket: Nam Kliang Wittaya School, Office of Secondary Education Service Area 28.
- Nipithpon Sanithluang, Watchariporn Satpech, and Yada Napharak. (2018). Sample size calculation using the G*POWER program. *Journal of Suvarnabhumi Institute of Technology*, 5(1), 497-507.
- Busara Boontala. (2020). The relationship between the use of information technology and the effectiveness of management in schools under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Bueng Kan. Master's Thesis, Sakon Nakhon: Sakon Nakhon Rajabhat University.
- Phakkorn Boonpan. (2020). The effectiveness of using information technology for management in schools under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Bueng Kan. Master's Thesis, Sakon Nakhon: Sakon Nakhon Rajabhat University.
- Pichayanee Kahleng. (2020). Guidelines for the use of information technology for management in basic education institutions under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Chaiyaphum, Zone 1. *Graduate Research Journal*, 11(1), 149-162.
- Worawut Larmjan. (2020). The state of the use of information technology in school management by administrators of private schools under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Phatthalung. *Proceedings of the 11th Hat Yai National and International Academic Conference*, Hatyai University, 224-236.
- Sarasas School Journal* (2017). *Sarasas School Connection Journal*, 15(26).
- Sitthichai Seeme. (2023). The necessary needs and development guidelines for using information technology for management in schools under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Sakon Nakhon, Zone 2. Office of the Secretary of the Education Council. (2017). National Education Plan B.E. 2560 - 2579. Bangkok: Prikwan Graphic.
- Office of the Secretary of the Education Council. (2021). Report on the study of learning management models for basic education students affected by the COVID-19 situation (Summary Edition). Bangkok: Prikwan Graphic Co., Ltd.
- Office of the Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Education. (2011). Master Plan for Information Technology and Communication for Education of the Ministry of Education B.E. 2554-2556. Bangkok: Ministry of Education.
- Usman Leesamhamat. (2017). Guidelines for using information technology for management in the Kiri Ratchat School group under the Office of Primary Education Service Area, Tak, Zone 2. *Mahachulalongkornrajavidyalaya University Journal: Northern College*